
EFFECTS OF INSIDER TRADING ON M&A DEALS - SEBI'S INVESTIGATION AUTHORITY AND IMPOSED PENALTIES

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ABSTRACT

This article explores an important professional concern of how India's laws on insider trading affect the due diligence processes that are utilized in the context of mergers and acquisitions, or "M&A Transactions." This article also briefly discusses the penalties for breaking insider trading rules and SEBI's investigative authority with respect to transactions that may have involved insider trading considering current occurrences.

I. INTRODUCTION

The act of trading in a publicly traded company's securities or one that is suggested for listing by someone with access to materially confidential information about the company or its securities that, if disclosed to the public, could affect the market price of those securities, is known as insider trading. Most countries forbid insider trading because it erodes investor confidence in the market. Prohibitions against insider trading are based on fair ideas that characterize transactions using important non-public information as either dishonest or fraudulent because of the insider's fiduciary duty to the common investor, or as contemptible because of uneven access to insider information². Anyone in India is prohibited from trading while in knowledge of material non-public information or from revealing such information, either directly or indirectly, by the Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992 (the "SEBI Act")³. The Securities and Exchange Board of India (the Securities and Exchange Board of India) passed the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015 (the "Insider Trading Regulations, 2015") in accordance with the SEBI Act. The Insider Trading

¹ Authors are law students at Amity University, Kolkata

² Cox, Bases of Insider Trading Law, <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/159577202.pdf>.

³ Section 12A, Securities and Exchange Board of India, 1992.

Regulations, 2015 are the primary regulations that govern and prohibit insider trading operations.

Furthermore, insider trading is prohibited by the Companies Act, 2013⁴, which prohibits insider trading by any parties, including directors and key administrative staff "of a company." Because of the ambiguous nature of this provision, it is possible to assume that insider trading is prohibited by company law for all companies, whether they are privately held, publicly traded, or publicly unlisted. It seems that such limits would be of limited use in the case of private and public unlisted enterprises (who do not seek to get their stocks listed) because of the absence of public participation in the price discovery of their securities. For this reason, there has been an attempt to strike this clause from the Companies Law (Amendment) Bill, 2016⁵.

II. AN OUTLINE OF THE LAWS PERTAINING TO INSIDER TRADING IN 2015

More than 20 years after the first major insider trading law in India was passed, in January 2015, the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992 (the "Insider Trading Regulations, 1992") were superseded by the Insider Trading Regulations, 2015. The Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 were passed following consideration of the recommendations made by a commission chaired by Justice N.K. Sodhi⁶. The definitions of "insider," "connected person," and "unpublished price sensitive information" (UPSI) were all expanded upon by these reforms, which also simplified disclosure events and permitted trading plans, among other notable improvements.

2015 regulations against insider trading forbade:

⁴ Section 195, Companies Act, 2013.

⁵ Section 63, Companies (Amendment) Bill, 2016.

⁶ Somasekhar Sundaresan, (Dec. 11, 2013), https://www.sebi.gov.in/sebi_data/attachdocs/1386758945803.pdf.

(a) **Trading⁷ while in possession of UPSI⁸**: Insiders are prohibited from trading in listed or planned-to-be-listed securities while in possession of UPSI.

(b) **Obtaining and Disseminating UPSI⁹**: Insiders are not allowed to provide, disseminate, or admit to any person access to any UPSI related to a company that is listed or scheduled to be listed, or its securities. Moreover, it is illegal for anyone to obtain or coerce an insider into communicating with UPSI. However, communication or procurement of UPSI is permitted in the interest of a fair cause, duty performance, or legal responsibility fulfilment.

The exemptions related to "legitimate purpose," "performance of duties," and "discharge of legal obligations" are not made clear in the 2015 Insider Trading Regulations. Additionally, they were absent from the 1992 Insider Trading Regulations, which permitted UPSI to be disclosed as needed by law or for the ordinary operation of a business, profession, or occupation. Since there isn't any guided legislation on the matter, it will be interesting to see how the regulator interprets these terms.

The Insider Trading Regulations of 2015 recognize that certain individuals, including senior managerial professionals and directors, may have continuous access to insider information about a company. These individuals can now make prearranged trading plans that run for a minimum of a year since trading plans¹⁰ were established. Trading plans ought to be disclosed to the public and adhered to strictly.

It is not permitted to trade the company's securities prior to the six months that follow the public announcement of the trading strategy¹¹.

The Insider Trading Regulations of 2015 require all promoters, directors, and senior executives of publicly traded businesses to provide initial and continuing disclosures.

⁷ Taxguru In, Comprehensive FAQs on SEBI (PIT) Regulations 2015, (Apr. 3, 2023), <https://taxguru.in/sebi/comprehensive-faqs-sebi-pit-regulations-2015.html>.

⁸ Regulation 4, Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

⁹ Regulation 3, Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹⁰ Regulation 5, Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹¹ <https://www.mondaq.com/india/compliance/1489972/regulatory-update-recent-amendments-to-the-insider-trading-regime>.

Initial Disclosure Requirement¹²: Any person owning company securities as of the appointment or promoter date is required to declare them within seven days of being appointed as a key managerial employee, director, or promoter of the firm, or after becoming a promoter themselves.

Continual Disclosure Requirement¹³: Every promoter, employee, and director are required to disclose the number of company securities acquired or disposed of within two trading days if the total value of the securities traded (in a single trade or in a series of trades over any calendar quarter) exceeds Rs. one million. In the event of a trade, the trading value of the derivatives will be considered.

Unlike the Insider Trading Regulations, 1992, the Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 do not require that (i) any individual holding 5% or more of the company's shares or voting rights—apart from promoters, directors, or key managerial personnel—disclose any acquisition or disposal that impacts the company's total shareholding or voting rights by more than 2%; and (ii) any individual holding 5% or more of the company's shares or voting rights disclose any change in the shareholding or voting rights of the company¹⁴. Furthermore, a listed corporation may, at its discretion, establish its own disclosure guidelines to make sure any associated parties are adhering to the rules.

III. THE PERMISSIBLE DISCLOSURES UNDER THE 2015 INSIDER TRADING LAWS AND THEIR EFFECTS ON MERGERS AND ACQUISITIONS

A. Permitted Disclosure

As previously stated, the Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 authorize communication and procurement of UPSI to perform obligations, comply with legal requirements, or further a legitimate purpose. In addition to the basic

¹² Regulation 7(1), Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹³ Regulation 7(2), Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹⁴ These disclosures continue to be required under the SEBI (Substantial Acquisition of Shares and Takeovers) Regulations, 2011.

limitations described above, the following transactions also allow the exchange and purchase of UPSI:

1. Where the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Substantial Acquisition of Shares and Takeovers) Regulations, 2011,¹⁵ require the making of an open offer the "Code of Takeover" If the board of directors of the company is of the informed opinion that the proposed transaction is in the best interests of the company, and the transaction involves the acquisition of control, 25% or more of the voting rights in a listed company, or more than 5% of the voting rights in a financial year where the acquirer already holds 25% or more of the voting rights in the company,¹⁶ additionally
2. When UPSI's information is made publicly available to the public at least two trading days before the proposed transaction is carried out, in whatever format the board of directors may determine, and the board of directors of the company is of the informed opinion that the proposed transaction is in the best interests of the company. This covers deals including asset purchases, slump sales, and other deals that are exempt from the Takeover Code¹⁷.

Before allowing any access under the above specified exceptions, the corporation is required under the Insider Trading Regulations 2015, to sign confidentiality and non-disclosure agreements with the persons acquiring access to UPSI¹⁸. Such people are also prohibited from dealing with the company's stocks in any other capacity while in possession of UPSI¹⁹. Consequently, the company would also be required to sign

¹⁵ Securities and Exchange Board of India (Substantial Acquisition of Shares and Takeovers) Regulations, 2011.

¹⁶ Regulation 3(3)(i), Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹⁷ Regulation 3(3)(ii), Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹⁸ Regulation 3(4), Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

¹⁹ Regulation 3(4), Securities and Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015.

standstill agreements, which would forbid anyone with access to UPSI from using UPSI for any other purpose or from trading in the company's stocks for a set period.

B. Impacts on Mergers & Acquisitions transactions

A long-standing ambiguity under the Insider Trading Regulations, 1992²⁰, which raised the possibility that information, including UPSI, shared by businesses with potential investors or acquirers during the due diligence process might be viewed as insider trading, has been resolved by the disclosures permitted by the Insider Trading Regulations, 2015. Performing due diligence prior to making an investment decision was crucial for prospective investors and acquirers, which presented real-world obstacles in investment and acquisition agreements. To make a reasonable investment decision in India, an acquirer or investor may need specific information and representations about the target company, as market disclosures from listed companies—such as quarterly results or even specifics of material contracts and transactions—may not be adequate. The SEBI recognized this practical problem and responded by introducing the exemptions listed in paragraph above. However, there are certain questions around these exceptions. Some points to consider are as follows:

1. Best Interests of the Company

The Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 mandate that the board of directors of a listed company decide whether a proposed investment transaction is in the best interests of the firm. In relation to this, the report of the committee headed by Justice N.K. Sodhi said that *“First, the board of directors will need to come to a clear view that permitting exercise of due diligence is in the best interests of the company. It is the company that is the owner of the UPSI*

²⁰ Sebi, Consultation Paper on Measures to strengthen index (Aug. 5, 2021), https://www.sebi.gov.in/legal/regulations/aug-2021/securities-and-exchange-board-of-india-prohibition-of-insider-trading-regulations-2015-last-amended-on-august-05-2021-_41717.html.

relating to the company and it should be the responsibility of its board of directors to justify permitting the conduct of a due diligence exercise.”²¹

In actuality, the parties do not sign legally binding agreements during the early phases of the transaction as the potential investor/acquirer performs a due diligence examination. Frequently, it could be too soon to say whether the suggested acquisition is optimal for the company. If new issue money is being received by the corporation, such an attitude could be created easily. In a secondary sale transaction—a shareholder selling firm shares to a third-party investment or acquirer might be challenging for the board of directors to take such a stand before notifying the investor or acquirer of UPSI. The identity of the new acquirer and the benefits of having them as a stakeholder in the company may be among the many considerations that the board of directors must consider in these circumstances.

2. **Disclosure of Board Decision**

Under the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Listing Obligations and Disclosure Requirements) Regulations, 2015, as amended (the "Listing Regulations"), listed companies are required to disclose to the stock exchanges any material events, such as any acquisition or agreement to acquire, as well as any sale or disposal of any unit(s), division(s), or subsidiary.²² The listed firm is also required to disclose the outcomes of all board meetings, which cover topics like shareholder and joint venture agreements that may have an impact on the management and control of the listed corporation.²³

²¹ Sodhi Committee Report, 28. - Bing, Search

https://www.bing.com/search?pglt=129&q=Sodhi+Committee+Report%2C+28.&cvd=11202fa2ce354def9bed98c6760101f9&gs_lcrp=EgRIZGdlKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOdIBBzg5NWowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531.

²² Regulation 30 read with Part A of Schedule III, The Securities and Exchange Board of India (Listing Obligations and Disclosure Requirements) Regulations, 2015.

²³ Regulation 30 read with Part A of Schedule III, The Securities and Exchange Board of India (Listing Obligations and Disclosure Requirements) Regulations, 2015.

So, the question is: If the board of directors of the listed company decides, after conferring with experts, that a proposed investment transaction is in the best interests of the target company, does it have to notify the stock exchanges of its decision?

Even though the Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 do not address this, it is still something to consider, especially considering that Indian stock exchanges have been actively contacting listed businesses to confirm or deny press reports about potential transactions. Due diligence is a preliminary step in the purchase process, and any information provided to the stock markets during this period could be misleading and encourage speculative trading. The listed company may determine that providing access to a potential acquirer or investor for the purpose of due diligence does not qualify as a significant event that has to be disclosed to the public if the parties have not executed a legally binding agreement to buy shares. An additional degree of security in this respect is provided by the confidentiality and standstill agreements that the investor/acquirer will have signed with the listed firm.

3. Public Release of UPSI Data

In transactions other than open offer transactions, the target entity is required to provide notice to the public of the UPSI at least two trading days prior to the day the "transaction is affected." This announcement, which ensures that all shareholders have equitable access to information, is sometimes referred to as a cleansing action. Nevertheless, it's not clear if the phrase "transaction is effected" refers to the day the official transaction documents are executed or the closing date, which is the day the shares are issued or transferred. The Sodhi Committee Report recommended that UPSI be released to the public at least two days prior to the scheduled "trading."²⁴ It makes it logical to make UPSI public before the final acquisition agreements are executed, but the target firm will have to decide when to do so. This is due to the possibility that in a secondary sale transaction, the target firm may be unaware of the

²⁴ Sodhi Committee Report, 28. - Bing, Search
https://www.bing.com/search?pgl=129&q=Sodhi+Committee+Report%2C+28.&cvid=11202fa2ce354def9bed98c6760101f9&gs_lcrp=EgRIZGdlKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOdIBBzg5NWowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531.

execution date of the definitive deal paperwork. Furthermore, it's likely that the target firm and the investor may argue over what information should be disclosed during these cleansing announcements because the target company's board of directors has the final say over the format and method of disclosure²⁵.

4. **Trade Mistake or Postponement**

The Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 do not specify how insider information discovered during due diligence should be handled if a deal involving an acquisition or investment is postponed or fails. Potential investors may still be barred from purchasing target business securities while UPSI remains under their control. Moreover, if the transaction has come to a halt, these declarations can cause problems for the target company.

IV. **THE INVESTIGATIVE POWER OF SEBI**

Because of the nature of the behavior, insider trading is hard to prove with hard evidence. Circumstantial evidence surrounding the transaction is the only basis for prosecution or punishment of an insider who divulges UPSI, trades with UPSI, or gains UPSI at the public's expense. In this sense, the SEBI's reach and application of its investigative powers become increasingly important.

Transactions that the agency believes have breached insider trading restrictions may be investigated under a wide range of authorities granted to it by the SEBI Act²⁶. The SEBI Act outlines the agency's duties, which include looking into and inspecting stock exchanges, middlemen, and other parties involved in the securities market. It also states that the agency is taking action to prevent insider trading and other unfair and deceptive trade practices. The SEBI Act delineates the duties of the agency, encompassing, but not limited to, probing and examining stock exchanges, intermediaries, and other entities implicated in the securities market; procuring data and documents from any source; and pursuing measures to proscribe insider trading and other inequitable trade practices.²⁷ The SEBI is also authorized to review any books, registers, documents, or records of a listed

²⁵ https://law.nus.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/004_2016_Umakanth.pdf.

²⁶ Sections 11(2)(i), 11(2)(ia), 11(2A) and 11C, Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

²⁷ Sections 11(2)(i) and 11(2)(ia), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

or soon-to-be listed firm if it has reasonable suspicions that the company engaged in insider trading²⁸. The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908²⁹, states that the SEBI has the same authority to do this as a civil court. These cover the capacity to gather data, create and review books of accounts and other documents, call witnesses or materials into question, summon them in person, question them under oath, and issue commissions to question witnesses or materials³⁰. SEBI may also act as an investigating authority and investigate the transaction, or the party involved if it has reasonable suspicions that transactions in the securities market are being handled in a way that is detrimental to investors or if any intermediary or person connected to the securities market has violated any laws or regulations of the SEBI Act³¹. If you do not cooperate with the investigating authorities, that is, if you do not give them any information or do not appear in person—you risk jail time and/or a fine³². According to the definition of "reasonable grounds to believe," a preliminary investigation ought to have supported a thorough review of the transaction at hand. The following are some examples of indicators that could give rise to a reasonable suspicion that the transactions were insider trading: unusually high daily trade volumes, trading near significant company announcements, or unexpected swings in stock prices.

It has been discussed whether SEBI has access to call data records (often called "CDRs") of certain individuals. In *Indian Council of Investors v. Union of India*³³, the Bombay High Court considered this issue and found that the SEBI has adequate authority under the SEBI Act to ask telecom service providers for CDRs. Unlike call interceptions, it was recognized that this information was static in nature. However, the court acknowledged that a fishing inquiry could not be conducted using SEBI's jurisdiction. It can only be utilized in the event of an ongoing investigation or inquiry by an officer who has been duly licensed in this regard. It is also advisable to get the officer's opinion in writing prior to making any requests for such information.

²⁸ Section 11(2A), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

²⁹ Section 11(3), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

³⁰ Section 11(3), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

³¹ Section 11(C), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

³² Section 11(C), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992

³³ *Indian Council of Investors v Union of India*, (2014) 186 Comp Cas 512. - Bing, Search [https://www.bing.com/search?pqlt=129&q=Indian+Council+of+Investors+v+Union+of+India%2C+\(2014\)+186+Comp+Cas+512.&cvid=35c525bcc83948579ab65c2ca4e1a919&gs_lcrp=EgRlZGdlKgYIABBFgdKyBggAEEUYOdIBBzc0MGowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531](https://www.bing.com/search?pqlt=129&q=Indian+Council+of+Investors+v+Union+of+India%2C+(2014)+186+Comp+Cas+512.&cvid=35c525bcc83948579ab65c2ca4e1a919&gs_lcrp=EgRlZGdlKgYIABBFgdKyBggAEEUYOdIBBzc0MGowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531).

The Securities Laws (Amendment) Ordinance, which was released in July 2013, September 2013, and March 2014, was recognized by the Bombay High Court in its decision. Previously, the only entities covered by the SEBI's investigative powers when it came to requesting information and records were the stock exchanges, mutual funds, banks, intermediaries and self-regulatory organizations in the securities market, any authority established under federal, state, or local legislation, and "any other person associated with the securities market." The SEBI's jurisdiction has been expanded by the ordinances, which permit it to obtain information from "any person." This position was reiterated in the SEBI Act's actual 2014 modification³⁴.

V. PENALTIES FOR VIOLATING INSIDER TRADING REGULATIONS

Insider trading is prohibited by the SEBI Act. A person involved in insider trading may be subject to legal prosecution in civil and criminal contexts.

A. CIVIL REMEDIES

If a violation of the Insider Trading Regulations 2015 is proven, the SEBI may, among other things, suspend the trading of the security, restrict or prohibit the accused individuals from accessing the capital markets, or impound and retain the proceeds or securities in relation to such a transaction. It may even do so in cases where investigations or enquiries into an insider trading transaction are still ongoing³⁵. Furthermore, an insider may be penalized up to Rs. 25 crore, or three times their profits from insider trading, whichever is higher, if it is established that they engaged in insider trading, disclosed insider information to unaffiliated parties, or enabled the trading of securities using insider knowledge. The fine can be more than Rs. 10 lakhs³⁶. Three variables are considered for determining the penalty amount: (a) the amount of disproportionate benefit or unfair advantage that resulted from the infringement; (b) the amount of loss incurred by the investment or investors; and (c) the repeated nature of the default.³⁷ Before the Securities Laws (Amendment) Act of 2014, the SEBI Act stated a penalty equal to

³⁴ The Securities Laws (Amendment) Act, 2014 issued with retrospective effect from July 18, 2013.

³⁵ Section 11(4), Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

³⁶ Section 15G, Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

³⁷ Section 15J, Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

three times the proceeds from the insider trading transaction or Rs. 25 crores, whichever was larger. While this would suggest that the SEBI had no discretion in imposing the punishment, in practice, mitigating circumstances—like the ones listed above—were regularly considered to reduce the fines related to the claimed infraction.

B. CONSENT ORDERS

Insider trading was another offence that may be handled by consent orders prior to the 2012 changes. Consent orders ensured that people suspected of insider trading may settle. Moreover, all the facts about the alleged insider trade may never be disclosed to the market. Insider trading has an impact on the market that goes beyond straightforward math. Consent orders and penalties would disgorge the accused person's gains, but they would not be enough to prevent future offences of the same nature or restore the faith that the market has lost because of insider trading legal disputes,³⁸ and they were like the severity of criminal accusations.³⁹ Sometimes, people view consent orders as a simple, fast method to wrap up legal matters and get fines. However, utilizing this technique in the case of crimes like insider trading has been deemed problematic because the accused would not even have to admit guilt or deny it⁴⁰. Moreover, all the facts about the

³⁸ SEBI Circular CIR/EFD/1/2012 dated May 25, 2012 - Amendment to the Consent Circular dated 20th April 2007. This circular has subsequently been rescinded and provisions thereof have been incorporated in the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Settlement of Administrative and Civil Proceedings) Regulations, 2014. - Bing, Search

[https://www.bing.com/search?pql=129&q=SEBI+Circular+CIR%2FEFD%2F1%2F2012+dated+May+25%2C+2012+-+Amendment+to+the+Consent+Circular+dated+20th+April+2007.+This+circular+has+subsequently+been+rescinded+and+provisions+thereof+have+been+incorporated+in+the+Securities+and+Exchange+Board+of+India+\(Settlement+of+Administrative+and+Civil+Proceedings\)+Regulations%2C+2014.&cvid=acf021eaf2664bf4a75a88a7c1959b4c&gs_lcrp=EgRIZGdIKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOdIBBzc3MmowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531](https://www.bing.com/search?pql=129&q=SEBI+Circular+CIR%2FEFD%2F1%2F2012+dated+May+25%2C+2012+-+Amendment+to+the+Consent+Circular+dated+20th+April+2007.+This+circular+has+subsequently+been+rescinded+and+provisions+thereof+have+been+incorporated+in+the+Securities+and+Exchange+Board+of+India+(Settlement+of+Administrative+and+Civil+Proceedings)+Regulations%2C+2014.&cvid=acf021eaf2664bf4a75a88a7c1959b4c&gs_lcrp=EgRIZGdIKgYIABBFgDkyBggAEEUYOdIBBzc3MmowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531)

³⁹ Consent order in respect of Lakshmi Energy and Foods Ltd, Judgment

<https://www.casemine.com/judgement/in/5d9b3b0a4a932678762df0db>

⁴⁰ Should Sebi have barred insider trading from consent orders? – Business Standard, (June 6, 2012), available at http://www.business-standard.com/article/opinion/should-se-bi-have-barred-insider-trading-from-consent-orders-11206060021_1.html (Last visited on July 31, 2016). - Bing, Search

[https://www.bing.com/search?pql=129&q=Should+Sebi+have+barred+insider+trading+from+consent+orders%3F+%E2%80%93+Business+Standard%2C+\(June+6%2C+2012\)%2C+available+at+http%3A%2F%2Fwww.business-standard.com%2Farticle%2Fopinion%2Fshould-se+bi-have-barred-insider-trading-from-consent-orders-11206060021_1.html+\(Last+visited+on+July+31%2C+2016\).&cvid=ef8d6cbbd9c941c59aa40fa1a341eea](https://www.bing.com/search?pql=129&q=Should+Sebi+have+barred+insider+trading+from+consent+orders%3F+%E2%80%93+Business+Standard%2C+(June+6%2C+2012)%2C+available+at+http%3A%2F%2Fwww.business-standard.com%2Farticle%2Fopinion%2Fshould-se+bi-have-barred-insider-trading-from-consent-orders-11206060021_1.html+(Last+visited+on+July+31%2C+2016).&cvid=ef8d6cbbd9c941c59aa40fa1a341eea)

alleged insider trade may never be disclosed to the market. Insider trading has an impact on the market that goes beyond straightforward math. Consent orders and penalties would disgorge the accused person's gains, but they would not be enough to prevent future offences of the same nature or restore the faith that the market has lost because of insider trading.

C. CRIMINAL REMEDIES

According to the SEBI Act, violating any of its guidelines, policies, or procedures could lead to criminal charges. A defendant facing infraction charges faces a maximum fine of Rs. 25 crore, ten years in prison, or both.⁴¹

Since the Insider Trading Regulations, 1992, were passed, very few insider trading instances have resulted in criminal prosecution⁴²:

1. 1998: The case involving Hindustan Lever Limited's directors.
2. 2002: The case of Rakesh Agarwal, managing director of ABS Industries Limited.
3. 2002: The matter concerning insider trading in securities of Sahney Paris Rhone Limited.
4. 2003: The insider trading scandal involving DSQ Holdings Limited.
5. 2003: Insider trading of Tata Finance Limited securities by J.E. Talaulicar, Dilip Pendse, and Jhunjunwala Stockbrokers.
6. 2003: The matter concerning fraudulent transactions and insider dealing involving securities of Information Technologies India Limited.
7. 2003: The fraudulent trading of V.B. Desai Financial Services Ltd. stocks by Kamlesh J. Shroff; and
8. 2010: The case involves Rajkumar Basantani's deceptive trading of Sound Craft Industries Limited securities.

5&gs_lcrp=EgRlZGdlKgYIABBFdKyBggAEEUYOdIBBzgyMmowajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=U531.

⁴¹ Section 24, Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

⁴² SEBI Data of Prosecution cases launched for violation of SEBI cases other than Collective Investment Schemes (As on May 31, 2016)

Still, not a single conviction has resulted from any of these legal procedures. Several legal actions are still pending in lower courts, notwithstanding the resolution of some cases—like those involving Sahney Paris Rhone Limited⁴³ and Rakesh Agarwal⁴⁴.

Criminal prosecution has the potential to be a potent deterrent in the securities market and encourage future compliance. That would not be appropriate, though, in every case of an alleged insider trading offence.

The decision to press charges in a particular case or not rests with the SEBI. The second question is what standards to apply and when to exercise this discretion. It is necessary to consider the procedure for determining whether a particular case calls for both criminal prosecution and a stronger level of deterrence that cannot be achieved by civil fines. The SEBI Act contains important factors to consider when assessing whether the penalties are reasonable, including the frequency of default and the extent of disproportionate gain or unfair advantage. Two other important factors could be the number of people affected by the transaction and the duration of the illegal activity. The low conviction rates in cases involving insider trading regulations would be a major factor in deciding the quantity of evidence required to prove misconduct in a criminal prosecution. Another factor to consider is the potential deterrent effect of criminal prosecution; if someone with fiduciary responsibilities is accused of breaking insider trading regulations, there may be a greater case for initiating criminal prosecution.

VI. CONCLUSION

Due diligence is an essential exercise that is completed before an M&A deal, and by making it clear that due diligence is acceptable, the Insider Trading Regulations, 2015 have greatly reduced the load on prospective investors and acquirers. However, bringing the regulations' exemptions into reality still presents practical difficulties. The challenges encompass determining the optimal course of action for the company, adhering to Listing Regulations when disclosing information to stock exchanges, managing insider information in the event of a deal failure or delay, timing, and the type and format of

⁴³ Sebi, News List All <https://sebi.gov.in/sebiweb/home/HomeAction.do?doListingAll=yes&cid=14>.

⁴⁴ SEBI v Rakesh Agarwal, Criminal Appeal No. 230 of 2007 (Bom).

cleansing announcements to the public. More guidance on these issues from the regulator is needed to give a stronger foundation for M&A transactions.

It is still challenging to locate these irregularities and gather evidence in these cases, even though the SEBI Act grants SEBI broad authority to investigate anomalies in the securities market, such as insider trading. Because criminal cases require a very high level of proof, this is particularly crucial. In this regard, the agency's authority has been further strengthened by the 2014 amendment to the SEBI Act. It remains to be seen how successful it would be to employ such expanded powers to handle complex institutions and technological developments that could be exploited to manipulate the market.

Likewise, the successful enforcement of insider trading laws in India depends not only on detecting insider trading but also on having a strong deterrent in place. Whether or not to file a criminal complaint in a particular insider trading instance depends on several factors. Given the challenges in obtaining evidence in insider trading cases, the high standard of proof required for successful criminal prosecutions, the historical trend of judicial pendency, and the low conviction rates of such offences, it is imperative that the regulator exercise its discretion in bringing criminal charges in a prudent manner.